

EVERYFISH

D5.7 Report describing what technical measures can potentially be removed under FDF

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Abstract

This report aimed to review the technical measures regulation (TMR) currently in force in the EU, based on those applying to Danish commercial vessels fishing with towed gears in Kattegat. Initially, the complexity of the TMR was assessed by making a comprehensive overview of the current regulations in Kattegat, including the objective and year of implementation for each regulation. Subsequently, a condensed overview was made of the technical measures and their aims using the categorization into input and output control defined by (Bellido et al., 2020). Each type of regulation was evaluated to determine whether electronic monitoring (EM) and fully documented fisheries (FDF) could achieve the same objective and thereby replace the regulation. The evaluation indicated that a large proportion of input regulations would become redundant under EM/FDF, whereas output controls such as quotas would remain necessary, suggesting that EM could facilitate a more result-based management framework. Similarly, an evaluation of the currently used control measures revealed that EM could replace a large proportion of these. Finally, this study emphasizes that the work carried out in this report should be expanded to other areas and fisheries, and that the alternative management frameworks should be tested in practice.

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission services)	
CI	Classified information (as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC)	

Deliverable type

R	Document, report	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC	Web sites, patent fillings, videos, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

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EVERYFISH consortium

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Executive summary

This report provides a review of the existing categories of technical measures and their Individual purposes and aims. The review is based on the technical measures regulation (TMR) currently implemented for Danish commercial vessels fishing with towed gears in Kattegat. The history and reasoning behind the implementation of the existing regulations is examined, as well as the level of complexity within the TMR. Based on the review of the TMR in Kattegat, it evaluates the necessity of the different regulations in a scenario where electronic monitoring (EM) cameras are introduced on the fishing vessels providing fully documented fisheries (FDF). The findings in this report suggests that most input regulations would become redundant, as EM would be able to fulfil the same aim as these regulations. Further it concludes that output measures such as quota systems will remain necessary, hence FDF could facilitate a shift towards result-based management. Finally, EM/FDF would be able to replace some of the existing control measures. The report advocates for expanding the work into other areas and other types of fisheries.

1. Introduction

1.1. EVERYFISH HEU motivation and background

The EVERYFISH project is a close collaboration between fisheries research, academic, industry, and governance actors, as well as technology providers across the EU and other European countries. These technological innovations will enable the fisheries sector to optimise automatic data collection and ensure correct reporting of the catch in terms of size, weight, and species. The provision of verifiable catch information and improved evidence of compliance with fisheries regulations will streamline compliance activities for both fisheries and regulators, as well as generating knowledge and data for future conservation, research, and governance activities.

EVERYFISH will build on and exploit the work done in multiple previous projects and further develop key technologies to increase their technology readiness level (TRL). In total, EVERYFISH will develop 10 products and apps for automatic catch recording and reporting, as well as guidelines for implementation and integration of EVERYFISH technologies in commercial fisheries in Europe to optimize resource efficiency, improve automatic data collection, provide evidence of compliance with fishery regulations, and reduce the ecological impact of the sector on the marine environment (Figure 1).

The methods and technologies developed in EVERYFISH will be ready for implementation in commercial fisheries. We assess their TRL in terms of the maturity of the underlying technologies in a fisheries context as several of them, e.g. AI, are already quite mature and used extensively in other sectors but still immature and relatively little used in fisheries management. All the products and apps developed in EVERYFISH are useful as standalone systems to provide automatic catch registration on vessels and by fishers that use them. However, their greatest potential will be realised when the data is standardized and automatically transmitted via a distributed ledger, to be used by stock assessors, fisheries monitoring and management agencies, certification companies, and others.

Figure 1: The conceptual structure of EVERYFISH HEU.

1.2. Role of the deliverable

This is the deliverable for **Subtask 5.3.1**: *DTU will review existing technical measures regulation within the European Union with the objective of understanding the reasons to why different regulation are in place, and under a FDF what aspects can be removed without compromising the sustainability of fish stocks.*

This subtask is the first part of **Task 5.3**: *Review present technical measures, and investigate fisher's perspectives* (lead: DTU; participants: WU; duration: M01–M12):

1.3. Structure of this document

This document is structured as follows:

- Background
- Methods
- Results
- Discussion
- Conclusion

1.4. Contributors

The following partners have contributed to this deliverable:

- DTU Aqua (DTU)

2. Background

2.1. Fisheries Management and Technical Measures in the EU

In the European Union (EU), fisheries management aims to ensure sustainable harvesting of fisheries resources in the long term. To achieve this objective, technical measures are adopted and enforced as part of the fisheries management framework known as the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP). Overall, technical measures aim to control the different aspects of fishing operations and are often categorized as either input or output control measures:

Input controls regulate the inputs to the fishery and include:

- Regulations of fleet characteristics and technical characteristics of fishing gear.
 - Technical characteristics of fishing vessels (e.g. length, engine power and tonnage).
 - Technical and operational characteristics of fishing gear (e.g. mesh size, twine thickness and requirement of selective gears etc.)
- Regulations of fleet access to fishing grounds.
 - Spatial and/or seasonal restrictions on fishing grounds.
 - Control of fishing effort.

Output controls governs the outcomes of the fishing operations which includes:

- Regulations of what can be caught and retained onboard.
 - Commercial minimum sizes (Minimum conservation reference size, MCRS).
 - Species composition: Allowed, vulnerable and prohibited species.
 - Quotas and catch limits (Bellido et al., 2020).

The first technical measures regulation (TMR) in the EU was adopted in 1998 (EU, 1998). This had frequently been criticized for being too complex, over-prescriptive and badly organized due to several exceptions and detailed specifications to the regulations (Kraak, 2022). In 2008, the European Commission made a proposal for a clearer and simpler TMR (COM, 2008). Subsequently, in 2012 the Scientific, Technical, and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) expressed that especially the gear specifications in the TMR were too complex and detailed (STECF, 2012). They argued that “a result-based approach focusing on the output rather than on the input may be a more effective approach” (STECF, 2012), and highlighted that this could be achieved with comprehensive monitoring and documentation of catches. The EU TMR currently in force was adopted in 2019 (EU, 2019), but despite the wish for a simpler regulation and result-based management, the complexity of the TMR still persists (Kraak, 2022). At present, only a very small percentage of all catches and fishing events are monitored and documented (van Helmond et al., 2020), hence it is impossible for management authorities as well as to the scientific community to know exactly what is extracted from the fish stocks. This can lead to the fishery not being assessed and managed according to expectation. Under

current conditions, technical measures are therefore necessary to limit fishing activities and reduce e.g. unwanted catches.

2.2. Technical measures in Kattegat

Kattegat is the body of water located between Denmark and Sweden (ICES Subdivision 21), connecting the North Sea/Skagerrak and the Baltic Sea. Kattegat has always been a highly important fishing area. Today the dominating fisheries in Kattegat are for Norway lobster, plaice and sole (ICES, 2023). Additionally, there was a directed fishery for cod in Kattegat until 2012. However, due to a very low abundance of cod, the cod quota in Kattegat has since 2012 been considered a bycatch quota (mainly in the fishery for Norway lobster)(ICES, 2023).

The quota system is currently the main regulation system for the Kattegat fisheries, however, the quantity and complexity of the TMR in Kattegat has increased remarkably in recent years. Until 2011, only the standard trawl gear was described in the Danish national regulation for Kattegat (a 90 mm codend with a 120 mm square mesh panel) (Retsinformation, 2010). In 2008, a cod management plan was implemented with the aim to help the cod stocks across the North Sea to recover, including the Kattegat cod. This management plan established several new management measures, including reductions in fishing effort (EU, 2008). Consequently, a Danish national cod recovery plan was established in 2010 (Kraak et al., 2013), allowing fishers to avoid effort reductions by increasing the selectivity of their gear. This led to several new selective gears being added to the TMR (e.g. different types of selection panels shown to reduce catches of cod). As another attempt to rebuild the cod stock, three important fishing areas in the South-East Kattegat were closed in 2009, due to an estimated high abundance of spawning cod found within these (Vitale et al., 2007; Kraak et al., 2013). However, the use of selective gears allowed fishers to maintain access to the otherwise closed areas in certain periods of the year, hence new selective gears like the Swedish grid and the Danish SELTRA 300 were added to the TMR (Kraak, 2022). The latest addition to the TMR happened in 2020 along with a project on electronic monitoring (EM) in Kattegat (Retsinformation, 2020b), specifying four legal gear options for the vessels without EM. To summarize, there has been several additions of new regulations, detailed specifications, and conditional derogations to the Danish national regulation in Kattegat since 2008, hence the current TMR is today highly complex and detailed (Table 1).

Table 1: Description of one of the legal gears in Kattegat taken directly from the Danish national regulation BEK nr. 1193 of 26/09/2023 (Retsinformation, 2023) and translated into English. This example is provided only to illustrate the complexity of the regulations.

BEK nr 1193 of 26/09/2023	"Swedish grid" with Maximum bar spacing of 35 mm.
<p>appendix 7 stk. 1.</p> <p>This gear can be used by bottom trawlers* with codend mesh size between 70 and 90 mm and additionally within two of the closed areas in Kattegat during specific periods of the year.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The grid shall be mounted in trawls with square-mesh codend with mesh size between 70 and 90 mm. Codend shall be at least 8m long. It is prohibited to use trawls with a circumference of more than 100 square meshes, excluding joinings and selvages. 2) The grid shall be rectangular. The bars of the grid shall be parallel to the longitudinal axis of the grid. The bar spacing of the grid shall not exceed 35mm. It shall be permitted to use one or more hinges in order to facilitate its storage on the net drum. 3) The grid shall be mounted diagonally in the trawl, upwards and backwards, anywhere from just in front of the codend to the anterior end of the untampered section. All sides of the grid shall be attached to the trawl. 4) In the upper panel of the trawl there shall be an unblocked fish outlet in immediate connection to the upper side of the grid. The opening of the fish outlet shall have the same width in the posterior side as the width of the grid and shall be cut out to a tip in the anterior direction along mesh bars from both sides of the grid width. 5) It shall be permitted to attach in front of the grid a funnel to lead the fish towards the trawl floor and grid. The minimum mesh size of the funnel shall be 70 mm. The minimum vertical opening of the guiding funnel towards the grid shall be 15 cm. The width of the guiding funnel towards the grid shall be grid width.

*Gear code: OTB, OTT, OT, TBN, TBS, TB, PTB.

2.3. Electronic Monitoring and Fully Documented Fisheries

In the past decade, there has been an increase in digital technologies for monitoring and enforcement in fisheries, such as electronic monitoring (EM) (van Helmond et al., 2020). Previously, it has only been possible to monitor and document the landed part of the catch, whereas now, EM cameras placed on the fishing vessel can remotely document entire catches and thereby provide fully documented fisheries (FDF) (van Helmond et al., 2020; Needle et al., 2015). Thus, EM has the potential to increase the monitoring and control of catches remarkably.

In 2019 a political decision was made, that EM cameras should be installed on the majority of Danish vessels fishing with towed gears in Kattegat (Danish Fisheries Agency, 2023b). This EM project was run by the Danish Fisheries Agency and started in 2020 where the first EM cameras were introduced on 12 voluntary vessels. In 2022, EM cameras became mandatory for all vessels fishing with towed gears with more than 20 fishing days in Kattegat (approximately 88 vessels in total) (Danish Fisheries Agency, 2023b). The background of the project was primarily the poor condition of the Kattegat cod stock, and the primary purpose was to document the fisheries for Norway lobster in Kattegat, especially with respect to the bycatch of cod. Additionally, the project aimed to assess how EM cameras would work in practice as a control measure (Danish Fisheries

Agency, 2023b). The project was ended and evaluated in October 2023 and how the project shall continue in the future is currently being decided upon. The Danish Fisheries Agency concluded in their evaluation that EM cameras are a very effective control measure, especially for documentation of entire catches (Danish Fisheries Agency, 2023b). When managers can have sufficient documentation on what is extracted from the ocean, the technical measures that specify details on how, when, and where to fish may become redundant. Therefore, having increased monitoring, control and enforcement could potentially simplify the current management frameworks and facilitate a more result-based approach to fisheries management (Kraak, 2022). Additionally, EM could potentially replace some of the existing control measures (i.e. last haul controls, onboard observers etc.) (Danish Fisheries Agency, 2023).

The purpose of this report is to review existing TMRs within the EU, based on the current TMRs in Kattegat, to understand the aim of the different regulations and the reasons for why they are in place. Furthermore, the different regulations are evaluated to see which regulations could be removed under FDF without compromising the aim of the regulations and hence the sustainability of fish stocks.

3. Methods

3.1. Overview of the TMR in Kattegat

A full overview was made of the current TMR in Kattegat applying to commercial vessels fishing with towed gear. This delineation was made as most of the current regulations in Kattegat, as well as the previously described EM project, are implemented for active fisheries (Danish Fisheries Agency, 2023b).

In the overview, the technical measures were categorized according to the classification described in section 2.1 (Bellido et al., 2020). The regulations currently in force for active gears in Kattegat were found in the official EU document of technical measures from 2019 (EU, 2019), and in the two Danish national regulations (Retsinformation, 2023; Retsinformation, 2020). Additionally, the aim of each regulation and the year of implementation was found in old national regulations and scientific papers describing the research leading to the implementation of a specific regulation.

3.2. Condensed overview of technical measures and control mechanisms

Based on the overview of the TMR in Kattegat, the different regulations were grouped according to their aim. Subsequently, it was evaluated whether EM cameras would be able to fulfill the same aim as the regulation and thereby simplify the present technical measures. In the evaluation it was assumed that EM cameras were introduced on fishing vessels and positioned in the sorting area to record entire catches. In this scenario, all video material from the EM cameras is being observed and all catches are being counted against the fishers' quotas. Throughout this report, "EM" will refer to EM cameras positioned in the sorting area of the vessels, hence not to other aspects of EM (i.e. various sensors, GPS or cameras placed elsewhere on the vessel (van Helmond et al., 2020)).

The necessity of each regulation was evaluated under the described scenario and given the color red, yellow or green based on the following criteria:

- Green: Under the described EM scenario, the regulation will remain necessary to fulfill the aim.
- Yellow: Under the described EM scenario, there are certain aspects which make the regulation necessary to fulfill the specific aim, and other aspects which make the regulation redundant.
- Red: Under the described EM scenario, the aim can be fulfilled without the regulation in place.

The category “Technical characteristics, length and engine power of fishing vessels” was not included in the table, as this category contains general regulations used to unify how the length, breadth, tonnage, engine power etc. of fishing vessels are measured across the EU. Hence this category was not seen as relevant for this evaluation. The EU regulations within this category are described in a separate EU document (EU, 2017).

Additionally, a table was made for the different control measures used in Denmark by the Danish Fisheries Agency to control fisheries: Last haul observations, harbor side controls, onboard observers, hygiene control and control of vessel engine power (Danish Fisheries Agency, 2023a). Similarly to the technical measures, each control measure was evaluated under the previously described EM scenario, and given either the color green, yellow or red, depending on their ability to replace the control measures. The evaluation of control measures was done based on the evaluation of the technical measures, meaning if certain regulations were evaluated as being redundant under EM, the measures to control these would be as well.

4. Results

4.1. Evaluation of Technical Measures

In the Kattegat TMR, the category “Technical and operational characteristics of fishing gears” contained by far the most regulations, which were additionally the most complex and detailed. The aim of each specific regulation was rarely stated clearly in neither the official EU documents nor the Danish national regulations, hence it was often necessary to investigate other sources to find the aim. The full overview of technical measures currently in force in Kattegat, can be found in Appendix 1, including references for each regulation and aim. The different categories of technical measures, their different aims, and the result of the evaluation under EM is presented in Table 2. Additionally, the reasoning behind the assigned color is stated in the table and the last column contains regulation IDs referring to specific regulations in the Kattegat TMR (Appendix 1).

Table 2: Condensed overview of the different categories of technical measures according to Bellido et al., 2020 and their different aims. The evaluation of the technical measures under EM is shown in column four "Is the regulation necessary under EM?". The regulations listed in the last column refer to specific regulations in Kattegat. These regulations, including their respective regulation ID, can be found in Appendix 1.

	TMR category	Aim	Example	Is the regulation necessary under EM?	Specific regulations in Kattegat
Input control	<i>Technical and operational characteristics of fishing gear</i>	Reduce catches of unwanted bycatch species	Selective panels and grids	The fishers will have an incentive to minimize unwanted catches when they are documented and recorded.	R3.1; R3.2; R3.3; R3.4; R3.5; R4.1; R4.2; R4.3; R4.4; R5.1; R5.2; R5.3; 6.1; R6.2; R6.3; R6.4; R6.5; R7.1; R7.2; R8.1; R8.2; R8.3; R9.1; R9.2; R9.3; R10; R11; R12; R13.1; R13.2; R13.3; R16; R17
		Reduce the catch of juveniles/small individuals of commercial species	Minimum codend mesh sizes		R1; R14; R15
		Reduce incidental capture of non-target species (charismatic and protected species)	Turtle exclusion devices (trawls), pingers (gillnets)		None
		Reduce seabed impact	Beam trawl prohibition in Kattegat	EM cannot monitor the seabed impact, hence input measure is required.	R2
	<i>Seasonal/spatial restrictions on fishing grounds</i>	Reduce disturbance of spawning activities	Closure 1, 2 (seasonal) and 3 (spatial) in Kattegat	EM cannot monitor the disturbance of spawning activities, hence input measure is required.	R19; R20; R21
		Reduce catch of spawning individuals	Closure 1, 2 (seasonal) and 3 (spatial) in Kattegat	The fishers will have an incentive to minimize unwanted catches when they are documented and recorded. Large individuals will with high possibility be spawning, hence these can be recorded on camera.	R19; R20; R21
		Reduce catch of juveniles	Real-time closures (RTCs)	The fishers will have an incentive to minimize catches of juveniles when they are documented and recorded.	None

		Protect vulnerable ecosystems and habitats	Bottom trawl closure in coastal areas (spatial)	EM cannot monitor the direct impact on ecosystems and habitats, hence input measure is required.	R18
	<i>Control of fishing effort</i>	Reduce fishing mortality	The use of fishing effort restrictions in the North Sea Brown Shrimp fishery	Effort regulations is often used without a quota system, which is needed for EM to create incentive.	None
Output control	<i>Commercial minimum sizes (MCRS)</i>	Protect juveniles of commercial species by ensuring that these cannot be sold commercially	MCRS on sole of 24 cm	Not required as fishers have no incentive to target small individuals, due to low market value. Required to ensure a market for juveniles does not develop and increase pressure on the smaller individuals.	R22; R23; R24; R25; R26; R27; R28; R29; R30; R31; R32; R33; R34
	<i>Allowed, prohibited and vulnerable species</i>	Avoid species extinction	Protection of salmon and seatrout in Kattegat	Necessary to define which species that are protected	R35; R36
	<i>Quotas and catch limits</i>	Ensure sustainable harvest of commercial fish stocks	ITQ (individual transferable quotas)	Necessary to provide incentive for fishers to use selective gears	R37; R38; R39; R40; R41; R42; R43; R44; R45; R46; R47; R48; R49; R50; R51; R52; R53; R54; R55

4.2. Evaluation of Control Measures

The result of the evaluation of control measures is presented in Table 3. This shows the different types of control measures and their respective aim(s). Similar to Table 2, the reasoning behind the color is stated in the table for each control measure and aim.

Table 3: Overview of the different control measures used by the Danish Fisheries Agency (Danish Fisheries Agency, 2023a). The evaluation of the control measures under EM is shown in the last column “Is the regulation necessary under EM?”.

Type of control measure	Aim	Is the regulation necessary under EM?
Last haul observations	Control of catch compositions (species, lengths, numbers)	EM can record catch compositions in regards to species, lengths and numbers.
Harbor side control	Control of catches	EM records entire catches.
	Control of gear specifications	Gear specifications are no longer necessary under EM.
Scientific onboard observers	Control of catch compositions (species, lengths, numbers)	EM can record catch compositions in both species, lengths and numbers.
	Sampling of biological material (individual weight, otoliths, genetics etc.)	Could be collected by fishers.
Hygiene Control (both at sea and in land)	Controlling if the fish is cleaned properly	Cameras can record whether fish are cleaned properly if placed in the right location.
	Controlling if the fish is cooled fast	Cooling will be difficult to monitor with cameras but could be done with remote EM sensors.
Control of vessel engine power	To ensure compliance with regulations on engine power	Could be done remotely with EM sensors.

5. Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the different categories of TMRs, considering that each type of regulation can have several underlying aims. The TMRs assessed were categorized into input controls: Technical and operational characteristics of fishing gear; Seasonal/spatial restrictions on fishing grounds; Control of fishing effort, and output controls: Commercial minimum sizes (MCRS); Species composition and Quotas and catch limits (Bellido et al., 2020). For each TMR and aim it was evaluated whether the introduction of EM cameras providing FDF would be able to fulfill the same aim as the regulation and thereby replace the current regulation.

The review of the TMR in Kattegat revealed that most of the current regulations were in the category "Technical and operational characteristics of fishing gears" (Table 2). Additionally, the regulations in this category contained the most detailed descriptions and were very complex to read, as illustrated in the example in Table 1. One of the reasons for the current complexity in the TMR may be that old technical regulations are seldom removed when new regulations are added (Kraak, 2022; STECF, 2012). Instead, new specifications, conditional derogations or exemptions may be added to the old regulations, as has been the case for the TMR in Kattegat: Even though several new gears have been added to the TMR, the old standard gear is still described in the regulation. However, now it is only legal in a specified period of the year, depending on the type of gear used (Retsinformation, 2023). This example from Kattegat illustrates how additions and conditional prescriptions to the regulations are making them grow in amount and complexity. Furthermore, the more we know about different factors affecting the selectivity of fishing gear, the more factors we need to include in the regulations (Eliassen et al., 2019). This is done to avoid that fishers can modify specific gear properties not specified in the legislation and thereby change the selectivity of their fishing gear (Krag et al., 2016). Based on the evaluation of the regulations related to technical characteristics of fishing gears, EM cameras would be able to fulfill the same aims as most of these (except those aiming to reduce seabed impact). As mentioned, the regulations within the gear category are the most abundant in Kattegat, more specifically those aiming to reduce catches of unwanted bycatch species (e.g. specifications on sorting grids and selection panels) (Table 2). Hence, if the technical gear measures aiming to reduce unwanted bycatch were replaced with EM cameras, it would have a large effect on the simplification of present the TMR in Kattegat.

Furthermore, some of the regulations in the category "Seasonal/spatial restrictions on fishing grounds" were evaluated as being redundant under EM: those with the aim of reducing catch of spawning individuals and reduce catch of juveniles, respectively (Table 2). Since cod is a highly quota limited species in Kattegat, there is a high risk of cod choking e.g. the fisheries for Norway lobster if it is caught in high numbers (ICES, 2022). If catches are recorded with EM and counted against the fishers' quotas, the fishers would have an incentive to avoid catching cod to keep fishing, hence the closures would not be necessary under EM. However, if the closures are made with the aim to reduce disturbance of spawning activities and/or vulnerable ecosystems and habitats, the regulation remains necessary as EM cameras cannot monitor the effect on other than what is caught. The same reasoning applies to the gear regulations with the purpose of reducing the seabed impact.

The last category of input regulations "Control of fishing effort", was previously used in Kattegat but was substituted by the selective gears (Kraak, 2022). Today, effort reductions are often used in fisheries that are not regulated by quota systems, as another way of putting a limit to the harvest of the fish stocks (e.g. the Brown Shrimp fishery in the North Sea) (Bellido et al., 2015). Common for all the regulations that were evaluated to become redundant under EM (marked with red in Table 2), is that for these to become redundant, it would require the presence of quota regulations. Under FDF and free gear choice, fishers would

lack an incentive to e.g. reduce catches of unwanted bycatch species, if their catches were not limited by quotas or catch limits (O’Keefe et al., 2014). In areas where fisheries are not regulated by quota systems, such as the Mediterranean Sea (Bellido et al., 2015), more input regulations would probably be necessary, and EM would not have the same effect on the regional management framework. To summarize, the evaluation of the TMR suggests that under EM a shift from input to output control would be possible, hence the transition to result-based management which was suggested as a more effective approach to fisheries management by STECF in already in 2012 (STECF, 2012).

Finally, the study aimed to assess which control measures could be replaced with EM. As is clear from Table 3, EM cameras would potentially render most of the current control measures redundant, especially if combined with other EM tools such as sensors and GPS (van Helmond et al., 2020). A limitation to EM, however, is that it will be insufficient to collect biological material from the fish such as otoliths, stomachs, and individual weights etc., which is needed for e.g. stock assessments (Needle et al., 2015). Nonetheless, this could potentially be collected by the fishers. In the evaluation of the EM project in Kattegat, the Danish Fisheries Agency concluded that EM is a very effective control measure, but that EM cannot stand alone as other control measures are needed to measure compliance with the gear regulations (Danish Fisheries Agency, 2023b). However, if gear regulations become redundant under EM, it would no longer be necessary to control these.

For future studies, the work presented in this report should be expanded to other areas and other types of fishing gears (e.g. static gears). Nonetheless, it is expected that the findings in this study are generic for most EU fisheries. Currently in the EU, there is a strong interest in implementing EM technologies in fisheries. The European parliament suggested in 2018 that EM shall be part of all larger commercial vessels operating in EU waters. In the present draft of the new control regulation it is stated that all vessels above 18 shall be equipped with EM before 2030 (EC, 2023). In a newly published report from the Danish Fisheries Commission from December 2023 (Fiskerikommissionen, 2023), they recommend that FDF should be implemented on all Danish commercial fishing vessels via the use of EM for real-time monitoring of catches. Their aim is that FDF shall be applied to the entire Danish fishing fleet as well as internationally and in the rest of the EU. As there may be several factors affecting the success of a shift towards result-based management under EM, it should be tested in practice how fishers will reach if certain regulations (e.g. gear regulations) are removed under EM.

6. Conclusion

This study revealed that under EM, most input regulations could become redundant. This would be a good possibility to simplify the current management framework, as the majority of the TMR falls under this category. However, output control such as quota systems would remain necessary under EM to provide the right incentives for the fishers to fulfill the same aims as the current input regulations. Additionally, EM could

replace several of the time-demanding control measures that are currently applied. This study should be expanded to include technical and control measures for other fishing gears and areas.

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8. Appendix 1

Appendix 1 - Kattegat Technical Measures 2023

Towed gears

INPUT REGULATIONS

Technical and operational characteristics of fishing gears								
Vessel type/metier	Gear	Description	Fishery/target species	Detailed specifications	Year that regulation came in force	Aim	Reference (the regulation currently in force is marked with "*")	Regulation ID
All	Legal baseline mesh size	> 120 mm or > 90mm	Not specified	May use smaller mesh sizes if: 1) bycatches of cod, haddock and saithe do not exceed 20% of total catch in live weight of all marine biological resources landed after each fishing trip 2) other selectivity modifications are used (see below)	2005	Reduce fishing mortality on cod, haddock and saithe	EU Regulation 2019/1241*; EU regulation 27/2005.	R1
All	Prohibited gear	Beam trawls	Not specified		1998	Protection of the seabed	EU Regulation 2019/1241*; EU Regulation 850/98, Article 39	R2
	Gear option 1/4: Sorting grid	"Svensk rist". Maximum bar spacing of 35 mm.	Not specified	The grid shall be mounted in trawls with square-mesh codend with mesh size between 70 and 90 mm. Codend shall be at least 8m long. It is prohibited to use trawls with a circumference of more than 100 square meshes, excluding joinings and selvages.	2020 (with the EM regulation)	Increase species selectivity. To avoid bycatch of cod and keep nephrops.	EU Regulation 2023/194*; BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 7*; BEK 1249 of 24/08/2020 appendix 13	R3.1
The grid shall be rectangular. The bars of the grid shall be parallel to the longitudinal axis of the grid. The bar spacing of the grid shall not exceed 35mm. It shall be permitted to use one or more hinges in order to facilitate its storage on the net drum.				R3.2				
The grid shall be mounted diagonally in the trawl, upwards and backwards, anywhere from just in front of the codend to the anterior end of the untamped section. All sides of the grid shall be attached to the trawl.				R3.3				
In the upper panel of the trawl there shall be an unblocked fish outlet in immediate connection to the upper side of the grid. The opening of the fish outlet shall have the same width in the posterior side as the width of the grid and shall be cut out to a tip in the anterior direction along mesh bars from both sides of the grid width.				R3.4				
It shall be permitted to attach in front of the grid a funnel to lead the fish towards the trawl floor and grid. The minimum mesh size of the funnel shall be 70 mm. The minimum vertical opening of the guiding funnel towards the grid shall be 15 cm. The width of the guiding funnel towards the grid shall be grid width.				R3.5				

Vessels fishing with bottom trawls (OTB, OTT, OT, TBN, TBS, TB and PTB) with minimum mesh size of 70 mm **with or without** EM (*stk 1*).

Gear option 2/4: Sorting grid	Maximum bar spacing of 50 mm.	Not specified	The grid is placed in bottom trawl gears of minimum of 90 mm. The codend must have a four meter long section for the release of roundfish mounted around the entire circumference of the codend. The section must consist of at least 125 mm square meshes and be positioned a maximum of two meters from the end of the codend (bindestrikken)	2020 (with the EM regulation)	Facilitate escape of roundfish while keeping flatfish. To protect cod.	EU Regulation 2023/194*; BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 7*; BEK 1249 of 24/08/2020 appendix 13	R4.1
			The grid shall be rectangular. The bars of the grid shall be horizontal in relation to the longitudinal axis of the grid. The bar spacing of the grid shall not exceed 50mm. It shall be permitted to use one or more hinges in order to facilitate its storage on the net drum.				R4.2
			The grid must be mounted vertically in the trawl. A tolerance of up to 25 degrees from the vertical plane is acceptable. It can be mounted just in front of the codend or further ahead in the extension piece. The grid must be attached to the trawl on all sides.				R4.3
			In the upper panel of the trawl there shall be an unblocked fish outlet in immediate connection to the upper side of the grid. The opening of the fish outlet shall have the same width in the posterior side as the width of the grid and shall be cut out to a tip in the anterior direction along mesh bars from both sides of the grid width.				R4.4
Gear option 3/4: selection panel	> 300 mm square mesh SELTRA panel	Not specified	Codend must be made of a square netsection with four sides of equal width.	2020 (with the EM regulation)	Reduce bycatch of fish (especially cod) to obtain a more clean catch of nephrops	EU Regulation 2023/194*; BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 7*; BEK 1249 of 24/08/2020 appendix 13	R5.1
			Sides must be made of diamond meshes with a mesh size of at least 90mm. Each side of the codend must consist of a maximum of 25 meshes, excluding those used for joinings and selvedges.				R5.2
			A three meter long selection panel must be placed in the top section. The end of the panel must be located maximally four m from the end of the codend. The panel must have a mesh size of at least 300 mm and consist of three open square meshes in width.				R5.3
			Codend must be made of a square netsection with four sides of equal width.				R6.1
			Sides must be made of diamond meshes with a mesh size of at least 90mm. Each side of the codend must consist of a maximum of 25 meshes, excluding those used for joinings and selvedges.				R6.2
			A three meter long selection panel must be placed in the top section. The end of the panel must be located maximally four meters from the end of the codend. The panel must have a mesh size of at least 300 mm and consist of three open square meshes in width.				R6.3

Vessels fishing with trawls in Area 1 from 1/1-31/3 (1st quarter) or in Area 2 from 1/4-31/12 (2nd, 3rd and 4th quarter)	Gear option 1/3: sorting grid	"Svensk rist". Maximum bar spacing of 35 mm	Not specified	Similar to the "svensk rist" described in BEK 1193 of 26/09/23 appendix 7 (see description above)	2009	Increase species selectivity. To avoid bycatch of cod and keep nephrops.	BEK nr 979 af 21/06/2020 appendix	R13.1
	Gear option 2/3: selection panel	> 300 mm square mesh SELTRA panel	Not specified	Almost similar to the SELTRA >300mm described in BEK 1193 of 26/09/23 appendix 7 (see above), but with following differences: Codend must be six meters in length. The end of the panel must be located maximally three meters from the end of the codend. Sides must be made of traditional meshes.	2009	Reduce bycatch of fish (especially cod) to obtain a more clean catch of nephrops	BEK nr 979 af 21/06/2020 appendix	R13.2
	Gear option 3/3: Topless trawl with selection panel	> 175 mm square mesh panel monteret in topless trawl	Not specified	Same SELTRA as described above (BEK 979 of 21/06/2020 appendix 4)	2010	Reduce fishing mortality for cod and haddock	BEK nr 979 af 21/06/2020 appendix 4*; BEK nr 391/2010 appendix 4	R13.3
Not specified	Minimum mesh size	16 mm	Small pelagic species		1998	Reduce catch of juveniles	EU Regulation 2019/1241*; EU regulation 850/98, Annex IV.	R14
	Minimum mesh size	16 mm	Norway pout (<i>Trisopterus esmarkii</i>)		1998	Reduce catch of juveniles	EU Regulation 2019/1241*; EU regulation 850/98, Annex IV.	R15
	Mandatory sorting grid	maximum bar spacing of 35 mm	Norway pout (<i>Trisopterus esmarkii</i>)		2019 (?)	Avoid unwanted bycatch	EU Regulation 2019/1241*	R16
	Maximum mesh size	16 mm	Sandeel		1998	Avoid unwanted bycatch	EU Regulation 2019/1241*; EU regulation 850/98, Annex IV.	R17

Spatial or seasonal restrictions to fishing

Vessel type/metier	Closed area	Period/duration of closure	Description	Exemptions	Year of implementation	Reason	Reference (the regulation currently in force is marked with "**")	Regulation ID
Not specified	The waters situated within 3 nm of the baselines	1/7 - 15/9	Codend mesh size of less than 32 mm is prohibited	Vessels carrying out directed fishing for Northern Prawn (<i>Pandalus borealis</i>) or fishing for use as bait of the species: eelpout (<i>Zoarces viviparus</i>), gobies (<i>Gobiidae</i>), or scorpion fish (<i>Cottus</i> spp.).	?	Seabed protection	EU Regulation 2019/1241*; more information in BEK nr 366 af 02/04/2019*	R18
Not specified	Area 1 (South east Kattegat)	1/1 - 31/3	Seasonal closure	1) Fishing for herring with pelagic trawls 2) Fishing with selective gears (see further details in gear-table above): 1) SELTRA >300 mm sorting panel 2) Topless trawl with SELTRA panel > 175 mm	2009	Protect cod spawning areas and spawning cod	BEK nr 979 af 21/06/2020*; [2]; [5]	R19
Not specified	Area 2 (within Area 1)	1/1-31/12	Partial closure	In the period 1/4 - 31/12: 1) Fishing for herring with pelagic trawls 2) Fishing with selective gears (see further details in gear-table above): 1) SELTRA >300 mm sorting panel 2) Topless trawl with SELTRA panel > 175 mm	2009	Protect cod spawning areas and spawning cod	BEK nr 979 af 21/06/2020*; [2]; [5]	R20

Not specified	Area 3 (within Area 1)	1/1-31/12	Permanent closure	None	2009	Protect cod spawning areas and spawning cod	BEK nr 979 af 21/06/2020*; [2]; [5]	R21
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OUTPUT REGULATIONS

Commercial minimum sizes (MCRS) and protected species				
Species	MCRS (cm)	Year of implementation	Reference (the regulation currently in force is marked with "*")	Regulation ID
Cod	30	1998	EU Regulation 850/98, Annex XII; [3]*	R22
Haddock	27	1998	EU Regulation 850/98, Annex XII; [3]*	R23
Saithe	30	1998	EU Regulation 850/98, Annex XII; [3]*	R24
Hake	30	1998	EU Regulation 850/98, Annex XII; [3]*	R25
Megrim	25	1998	EU Regulation 2019/1241*; EU Regulation 850/98 Annex XII	R26
Sole	24	1998	EU Regulation 850/98, Annex XII; [3]*	R27
Plaice	27	1998	EU Regulation 850/98, Annex XII; [3]*	R28
Whiting	23	1998	EU Regulation 850/98, Annex XII; [3]*	R29

Norway lobster	Total length: 105 mm Tail length: 59mm Carapace length: 32 mm	2016 (reduced from 40mm carapace length)	EU Regulation 2019/1241*; [6]	R30
Mackerel (1)	20	1998	EU Regulation 850/98, Annex XII; [3]*	R31
Herring (1)	18	1998	EU Regulation 850/98, Annex XII; [3]*	R32
Horse mackerel (1)	15	1998	EU Regulation 2019/1241*	R33
Lobster	Total length: 220 mm Carapace length: 78 mm	1998	EU Regulation 2019/1241*	R34
Spiny dogfish	> 100 (Immediate release)	?	[3]*	R35
Salmon and sea trout	protected	1998	EU Regulation 2019/1241*. EU regulation 850/98, article 36	R36

Quotas (catch limits)			
Species	Quota type	Reference (the regulation currently in force is marked with "**")	Regulation ID
Cod	FKA	BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 13*	R37
Haddock	FKA	BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 13*	R38
Saithe	-	[9]	R39
Hake	-	[9]	R40
Sole	FKA	BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 13*	R41
Plaice	FKA	BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 13*	R42
Whiting	-	[9]	R43

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Norway lobster	FKA	BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 13*	R44
Mackerel (1)	ITQ	BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 13*	R45
Herring (1)	ITQ	BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 13*	R46
Sandeel	ITQ	BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 13*	R47
Norway pout	ITQ	BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 13*	R48
Northern prawn	FKA	BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 13*	R49
Sprat	ITQ	BEK 1193 of 26/09/2023 appendix 13*	R50
Skates, rays	-	[9]	R51
Argentine	-	[9]	R52
Ling	-	[9]	R53
Blue ling	-	[9]	R54
Roundnose grenadier (<i>Coryphaenoides rupestris</i>)	-	[9]	R55

FKA = Fartøjs Kvoteandele
ITQ (dansk: iØK) = Individual transfereable quotas
(1): shall not apply within allimit of 10% by live weight of the tott. catches retained on board of each of those species (derogation to article 15 of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013

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